

MODERN METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING
METHODOLOGY

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Abstract: This article discusses the methodology of foreign language teaching, the history of its development as a science, the types of modern methods used in foreign language teaching methods and their use.

Keywords: methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skills, competencies, didactics, intercultural communication.

Introduction.

Modern educational development has given rise to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative - means "introduction (dissemination) of innovation" in English. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American researcher E. Rogers. He studied the classification of innovation process participants, their attitude to innovation, etc. The concepts of novelty and innovation are mutually different in scientific areas. "Innovation" means a tool, new method, methodology, technology. "Innovation" is a process that develops according to certain stages of education. The development of world science is growing and developing day by day. It was this positive development that affected our country as well. Advanced innovative technologies are being applied to our world of science. As a result of this, our President named this year "The Year of Youth Support and Public Health", which increased the responsibility of the youth of our country. It would not be a mistake to say that the wide application of advanced, modern innovative technologies in the field of education has opened the door to many opportunities and goals for young people learning foreign languages.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, in the community or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in our time of increased international relations. Pupils and students studying in our country usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of brothers and neighbors of other nationalities.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European languages (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our republic. These languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions. The process of teaching all three languages is different. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language mainly takes place in the classroom under the guidance of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs sharply in certain aspects. This, in turn, requires the use of

appropriate foreign language teaching technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of the methodical science, the foreign language teacher gets to know the standard of language experience of the student and to improve it further. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology. Learning and teaching foreign languages largely depends on the theoretical development of foreign language teaching methodology issues and the creative application of theory in practice.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The phenomena of nature and society are interconnected and develop in a continuous relationship. Since the sciences are reflections of objective reality, none of them exists in isolation from the others. At the same time, the phenomenon and the subject can be a source of research for many sciences, for example, linguistics (linguistics), psychology (psychology), pedagogy (didactics) study the social phenomenon "language" from its own point of view. The term "foreign language methodology" evokes the following association in a person's mind: first of all, it is understood as a set of methods and methodical methods aimed at teaching a language, or scientific knowledge about teaching methods, and finally, independent pedagogy. science comes before our eyes. The methodology of foreign language teaching has developed in harmony with didactics. It is undoubtedly known to all of us that the teaching theories of all educational subjects are based on didactics science and receive scientific nutrition from it. Foreign language teaching is also based on didactics. Didactics is the general theory of education, methodology is the science of teaching a specific subject, linguodidactics is the general theory of language teaching, and linguomethodology is the science of teaching a specific language. The term "Method" means the method of work of the teacher-pedagogue and the student in order to acquire knowledge, skills, and create worldviews and knowledge opportunities in students. This concept has countless definitions. The application of methods in foreign language teaching has been around for a long time, and principles are relatively new methodological terms. Historically, the methods were grouped into four groups, and their names were called "translation", "correct", "comparative", "mixed".

The history of methods is the famous methodist prof. Deeply studied by I.V. Rakhmanov. The method of translation is mainly in two forms, and it is called grammar-translation and text-translation methods. From the point of view of the grammar-translation method, a foreign language is studied for general educational purposes. Grammatical exercises are performed in order to develop the logical thinking of the language learner. Expressing grammatical knowledge is considered to be the main goal of education. The main principles of this method are as follows:

1. Language learning is based on written speech.
2. Grammar was taken as the subject of study, and the lexicon was chosen accordingly. Grammar exercises were the main method of work.
3. First, grammatical rules were memorized, and then it was recommended to make sentences based on the rules.
4. Grammatical forms and the meaning of words are revealed through literal translation.

5. Language material is mastered by literal translation and dry memorization.

6. Limited to individual memorization of words out of context.

Method without translation. Different forms of this method are known historically. They can be divided into two large groups: natural and correct methods. Learning a foreign language in a natural way should be similar to the conditions of mastering the mother tongue. The main goal of the method is the idea that by learning to speak a foreign language, it is possible to learn to read and write. The most important of the principles included in the natural method is to create a language environment. Various approaches have appeared in the practical application of the advanced methodical principles. This can be clearly seen in the creative activity of the method exponents.

The new interpretation of the purpose of foreign language education was mainly based on the results of pragmatic linguistics research. This field of linguistics interprets language as a field of human activity rather than a system of linguistic forms. In the field of foreign language education, since the beginning of the 70s, a set of new conclusions has led to intense discussions in the field of educational goal setting.

Conclusion.

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted discipline, in which a person undergoes complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are: communicative didactic method, intercultural dialogue organization method and exercise organization method. All three methods are closely related and complement each other. Since the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, it is based on communicativeness during foreign language learning and the method of communicative didactics is created. In the process of applying the method of communicative didactics, the teacher's method of forming intercultural communication is formed. As a result of learning a foreign language, the culture of a foreign country is also learned. In order to acquire the necessary knowledge in foreign language education, "exercise organization technology" is of great importance.

Practice is the best way to master all knowledge. The exercise gives a positive result not only in foreign language education, but also in the acquisition of knowledge in all fields. Effective organization of the lesson, the role of the pedagogue and modern pedagogical technologies in it is incomparable. It is important to organize the process of learning a foreign language with a communicative approach, to bring the next level to the level of intercultural communication, and to achieve such results, it is important to pay attention to the last step, "exercise technology". Teaching a foreign language in order to effectively organize the process, it is necessary to acquire knowledge of modern pedagogical information and communication technologies.

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